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AXIS 3. Teaching design in the age of digital intelligence: pedagogical hybridizations and critical perspectives

Title: Augmented creativity: AI in training tomorrow's designers

Introduction

The integration of generative artificial intelligence into the educational landscape has triggered a profound transformation in university learning and teaching methods. This evolution has paved the way for an unprecedented synergy between pedagogy and digital technology, focused on personalization, adaptability, and creativity (Urmeneta and Romero, 2024). However, even though the advent of GAI and its widespread use among a large proportion of students offer immense potential, its integration raises fundamental questions about the development of critical thinking and creativity in learners, as well as inviting teachers to redefine learning objectives and rethink current strategies applied in design education.

Generative artificial intelligence (GAI), with its ability to produce text, images, code, or music, embodies this promise. It offers immense potential, such as intelligent tutoring and adaptive assessment, providing valuable support for differentiated instruction. However, this technological revolution is not without its ambivalence. Its integration raises fundamental questions about the skills to be developed in learners, beyond simple technical mastery. The risk of homogenization of the creative process, coupled with issues of intellectual property and “intellectual laziness,” calls for increased vigilance. As Guitton and Romero (2021) point out, it is imperative to move beyond a purely instrumental vision to articulate three axes: personalized adaptive learning, AI as a computational model of cognitive processes, and civic and critical teaching of AI.

The integration of AI into education seems to be steering universities towards the implementation of a teaching model focused on human skills that AI cannot replicate, which advocates for increased personalization of learning and a profound reconfiguration of the teaching profession. Far from being a threat, by freeing teachers from repetitive tasks, AI could allow them to focus on more creative and constructive activities, such as redefining learning objectives and assessment methods, or helping learners develop technical skills to master AI tools and prompting techniques.

The aim of this article is to understand what literacies or transliteracy AI tools require in order to promote truly creative uses, and what teaching strategies teachers should use to ensure that AI tools can be used effectively in design education.

To answer these questions, we will establish a state of the art by defining the pedagogical potential of AI and the critical challenges it raises. By articulating the concepts of personalization, digital creativity, and transliteracy, we will highlight the potential of using AI in design education as well as the challenges and risks of standardization. Secondly, we will present and analyze the results of a qualitative study conducted with a sample of design

teachers from ESSTED and the higher institutes of fine arts in Tunis, Nabeul, and Sousse in order to understand teachers' perceptions and their use of AI. This analysis will reveal existing skills, gaps, and strategies implemented with students. Finally, we will present a case study of the FAM project that took place in Guermessa in 2025, which aimed to highlight the role of design in promoting rural craft heritage through, among other things, AI tools in order to develop greater autonomy and creative power in learners.

1. Conceptual framework: the potential of AI tools between promises and challenges

The arrival of AI in the educational ecosystem is often seen as an opportunity to radically rethink teaching practices. The work of Guitton and Romero (2021) identifies several major areas of integration. AI makes it possible to dynamically adjust educational pathways to the individual needs of students, offering tailored exercises, resources, and feedback. By modeling learning mechanisms, AI can help optimize teaching strategies and better understand learners' difficulties. The arrival of AI also invites teachers to rethink the very idea of creativity, which Jeanneret (2014) defines as a process conditioned by social, cultural, and technical logics. Digital creativity is now inseparable from transliteracy, the ability to navigate, evaluate, and create information across different media, formats, and languages in changing socio-technical contexts (Frau-Meigs, 2019). In this context, AI could bring about a beneficial restructuring of roles. By automating repetitive tasks (basic corrections, generation of standardized materials), AI frees up teachers' time to focus on higher value-added activities: personalized support, facilitating critical debates, and facilitating creative and collaborative projects (Bazile et al., 2024). Teachers would thus evolve from transmitters of knowledge to mediators, guides in a complex informational and technological landscape.

To understand the impact of AI on creativity, it is also essential to define it as a social and technical process that involves a transformation of meaning and usage. In the digital environment, this creativity is closely linked to transliteracy (Frau-Meigs, 2019). It is at the heart of the collaborative and "updated" forms of expression that characterize digital culture, where creation often emerges from the reappropriation of existing content, in a logic of editorialization and peer recognition. AIAs fit perfectly into this logic of hybridization, but on an unprecedented scale and with unprecedented power. They could become algorithmic co-creators capable of generating infinite variations from prompts.

The user's creativity then shifts partially from direct execution to curation, guidance, and iteration with the machine.

In addition, AI is able to offer remarkable opportunities for differentiation and personalization of learning. This ability to adapt is a significant lever for supporting the heterogeneity of student profiles. The automatic generation of exercises, course materials, and assessment grids allows teachers to devote more time to personalized support and facilitating collaborative activities (Machuré et al., 2024). This flexibility could pave the way for a rethinking of the role of the design teacher, who would become a mediator guiding learners to properly exploit the potential of AI while developing their own creativity in an educational approach focused on the development of critical thinking and creativity. In this new pedagogical relationship, teachers would evolve into a new model where they would be architects of learning situations and facilitators of interaction with knowledge (Romero et al., 2022).

However, while AI offers considerable advantages in terms of creation, visualization, and sharing, it runs the risk of standardizing and homogenizing the creative process. The “black box” of technology poses several problems: What data was used to train the model? Does it reflect a diversity of social and cultural norms, or does it reproduce biases and stereotypes? Poorly indexed or unrepresentative data could distort the accuracy and originality of the results (De Sousa Cardoso and Parise, 2023).

The creative process risks becoming a solitary interaction with a machine, to the detriment of the collaborative, remixed, and socially situated dimensions that are essential to artistic learning (workshops, peer review, informal exchanges). The ease with which AI generates impressive results can create an illusion of mastery and discourage the deep cognitive effort, risky experimentation, and formative error that are at the heart of creative development (Moinard, 2024). In light of this observation, the need to develop critical digital skills in young people and teachers has become a priority (Claro, 2025). It is no longer just a matter of knowing how to use a tool, but of developing a mastery that allows it to be questioned, repurposed, and thoughtfully integrated into a personal creative process. Teachers must therefore develop in students the ability to question the sources, potential biases, and limitations of the outputs generated. This critical stance is an essential complement to the technical use of tools. The issue of teacher training therefore appears to be an essential prerequisite for any efficient use. The work of Piekoszewski-Cuq (2024) highlights the need for continuous professional development to enable teachers to appropriate these technologies in an informed manner. This training must transcend simple technical mastery to encompass the ethical, epistemological, and pedagogical dimensions of AI integration.

The efficiency of teachers' use of AI tools thus lies in this subtle balance between exploiting their pedagogical potential and maintaining a critical distance. It is a matter of using these technologies as levers to serve pedagogical objectives, while cultivating constant reflexivity about their conditions of production and their educational implications. This balanced approach avoids systematic rejection, paving the way for a reasoned and truly transformative integration of AI into teaching practices. This perspective is consistent with the observations of Mourtajji and Arts (2025) on appropriation profiles, suggesting that the most fruitful uses emerge when teachers manage to integrate AI tools into a comprehensive and thoughtful pedagogical approach, where technology remains at the service of clearly identified educational goals.

2. Qualitative study

2.1. Methodology

In order to explore the representations and teaching practices related to the integration of generative artificial intelligence in university design education, we chose a methodology that focuses on gaining an in-depth understanding of the experiences of educators directly confronted with this technological transformation. The study was conducted with eight university teachers working in Tunisian higher education institutions specializing in arts and design. Participants were selected using a reasoned sampling method aimed at capturing the diversity of teaching profiles, including assistant professors, teacher-researchers, and adjunct teachers, all involved in training for creative professions.

Respondents	Rank	Institution	Professional use of IA	IA training
1	Substitue teacher	ISBAT	Yes	Auto-Training
2	University professor	ISBAT	Yes	Auto-Training
3	University Researcher	ISBAN	Yes	Auto-Training
4	University professor	ISBAN	Yes	Auto-Training
5	Substitue teacher	ISBAS	Yes	Auto-Training
6	Assistant Professor	ISBAS	No	Auto-Training
7	Assistant Professor	ESSTED	Yes	Auto-Training
8	University Researcher	ESSTED	Yes	Auto-Training

Table 1: List of respondents

Data collection was based on semi-structured interviews, which allowed us to maintain a common focus while retaining the flexibility necessary for individuals to express their unique perspectives. The interview guide, structured around predefined themes, ensured the comparability of responses while allowing for unexpected developments. The main areas of investigation concerned everyday digital practices, representations of generative AI, concrete methods of use in educational activities, self-training processes, and prospects for the institutional integration of these technologies. This analysis highlighted nuanced positions regarding the creative potential of generative AI, while revealing shared concerns about the educational and ethical challenges raised by its integration into arts training. The qualitative approach adopted made it possible to grasp the complexity of teachers' positions in the face of the emergence of generative AI in the educational ecosystem of arts and design.

The sample presents a diversity of academic profiles, ranging from adjunct teachers to assistant professors and teacher-researchers, spread across several specialized institutions. This variety allows us to understand the phenomenon from different institutional and statutory perspectives. The analysis shows that seven of the eight teachers surveyed actively use generative AI in their professional practice, indicating relatively widespread adoption despite the recent nature of these technologies. The only teacher who does not use AI nevertheless recognizes its creative potential, highlighting a general openness even among non-users.

2.2. Analysis of results

Analysis of the results shows that the majority of teachers express an ambivalent perception of generative AI, oscillating between enthusiasm for its potential and caution about its limitations. Several participants describe these tools as “extraordinary” but “frightening,” recognizing both their creative power and the risks associated with their use. Respondent 3 expresses this ambivalence with nuance: “Digital technologies offer undeniable advantages in terms of ease of use, but authentic creativity often finds its essence in manual manipulation.” This position reflects a search for balance between technological innovation and the preservation of the fundamentals of artistic creation. The analysis also reveals three main ways of integrating AI into teaching practices, including use as a creative assistant, use as a productivity tool, and use as a creative stimulator, where AI serves as a “brainstorming tool” to unlock ideas or suggest unexpected alternatives. Respondent 5 refers to a creative synergy:

“Exchanging with AI via different prompts to discover exceptional results.” This approach illustrates a complementary rather than substitutive vision of AI in the creative process. Respondents identified several major educational challenges. The issue of standardization of results appears to be a central concern, with fears about the homogenization of student work. There is also the difficulty of maintaining a critical mindset when faced with perceived tools. Respondent 6 expresses this vigilance: “I remain convinced that the university will not be overtaken by these fads,” reflecting the need for a thoughtful approach rather than uncritical adoption.

With regard to training, there is unanimous agreement: all teachers who use these tools have resorted to self-training, mainly through online tutorials and platforms such as YouTube. The lack of institutional training appears to be a significant shortcoming, with several participants (2.6) calling for investment by institutions in this area in terms of tools, software, and training within our various institutions to train teaching staff. In addition, respondents (3.5) propose various approaches for the successful integration of AI into teaching. Project-based learning emerges as the preferred method, allowing for practical experimentation coupled with critical thinking. The need to adapt assessment methods is also highlighted, with a shift towards skills such as prompt engineering and critical analysis of outputs. Respondent 8 summarizes this evolving vision by stating that “Teachers must become facilitators, critical mediators, and designers of innovative learning situations.”

This transformation of the teaching role appears to be an essential condition for successful pedagogical integration. Thus, analysis of the attitudes and practices of the eight teachers reveals a pedagogical community in transition, navigating between technological opportunism and the preservation of the fundamental values of arts education. The adoption of generative AI seems to follow a logic of gradual appropriation, where tools are integrated as complements rather than substitutes for human creativity. Several teachers highlight the ability of AI to restore autonomy to students who previously required constant support. According to respondent 4, “A dyslexic student can now use AI to check and improve their written work without constantly having to rely on the teacher.” They believe that this form of digital support allows for better integration into group work and collective activities. To realize this inclusive potential, teachers emphasize the need to develop specific skills in engineering prompts tailored to different needs. They also call for close collaboration between digital specialists, educators, and disability professionals to design truly effective tools.

Thus, the majority of teachers express an optimistic view of the use of AI. However, they denounce the lack of a clear institutional framework and stress the need to develop structured support strategies for teachers. The fundamental challenge appears to lie less in technical mastery of the tools than in the development of a critical pedagogy capable of exploiting the creative potential of AI while preserving the autonomy and critical thinking of learners.

3. Case study: FAM project

3.1. Active teaching and student awareness

The FAM (Femme & Artisanat en Médiatisation) project is an innovative initiative at the intersection of design, heritage, and digital technology. Led by LUCID in partnership with ESSTED and ILEF, with the support of Wallonie-Bruxelles International, this ambitious project aims to preserve and promote the tangible and intangible heritage of the Amazigh village of Guermezza, in the governorate of Tataouine. The unique feature of this approach

lies in the active involvement of design students and the strategic use of digital technologies, including artificial intelligence, to document, analyze, and revitalize a cultural heritage that is in danger of disappearing.

Figure 1: exchanges between designers and artisans

As part of a multidisciplinary collaboration, the FAM project revolved around a series of workshops designed as spaces for co-creation between local artisans, researchers, and students from the Master's program in Design for Sustainable Development. These activities allowed for deep immersion in the cultural ecosystem of Guermessa, with the specific objectives of documenting traditional weaving techniques, 3D digitizing carpets and artisanal gestures, and conducting a semiotic analysis of Amazigh symbols. This immersion phase provided an essential foundation for understanding the complexity of the local heritage in its technical, social, and symbolic dimensions. The second workshop in Denden marked a crucial step in the promotion process by welcoming the weavers to Tunis. This reversal of traditional dynamics led to institutional recognition of their expertise while creating a fruitful dialogue between the custodians of this heritage and academic stakeholders. The 21 master's students were actively involved in an ethnographic investigation, combining participant observation, interviews, and multimodal data collection to understand the three fundamental aspects of Guermessa's heritage: weaving and vegetable dyeing, food and culinary practices, and vernacular troglodytic architecture.

Figure 2: Heritage enhancement

The uniqueness of this project lies in the strategic integration of digital technologies as tools for preservation and mediation. The 3D digitization of artifacts, technical gestures, and architectural spaces has made it possible to create accurate and interactive digital archives, constituting a living memory of endangered heritage. This documentation goes beyond simple conservation to become a collaborative working tool, enabling different stakeholders to manipulate, analyze, and reinterpret heritage elements from an innovative design perspective. Artificial intelligence played a decisive role in the semiotic analysis of Amazigh geometric patterns. The study of symbols benefited from AI's pattern recognition capabilities to decipher complex symbolic systems and their contextual variations. This computational approach revealed semantic connections between different cultural expressions (textiles, architecture, tattoos) that often escaped direct human observation. Modeling the collected data facilitated the design of an optimized experiential tourist route, holistically integrating cultural, social, and environmental dimensions. Digital tools made it possible to simulate different development scenarios, assess their impact on the local community, and design immersive experiences that respect heritage while being economically viable.

3.2. Project to set up a virtual museum

This educational approach involved the learners in active learning, placing them in the role of cultural mediators who had to translate the complexity of the heritage into concrete proposals for its promotion. This project-based learning experience confronted them with the real challenges of sustainable development: cultural preservation, social equity, economic viability, and environmental respect.

Under the direction of Neila RHOUMA, assistant professor at ESSTED, and in collaboration with several stakeholders, teachers, and students, as well as a multidisciplinary team of ethnologists, designers, architects, and philosophers, an ambitious project was brought to fruition: the use of 3D scanning and photogrammetry made it possible to reproduce, archive,

and preserve handcrafted objects so that they could be integrated into a virtual museum tour that is both realistic and innovative. This approach reflects an efficient and positive use of artificial intelligence, which transforms IAGs into a tool for cultural transmission.

The approach taken was based on a rigorous digital capture process. The 3D scanning of the handcrafted artifacts—including traditional weaving tools, carpets, looms, and textile pieces—was carried out using photogrammetry scanning technologies. This technique made it possible to capture not only the geometry of the objects, but also their material properties. This made it possible to record the characteristics of the objects in order to faithfully reproduce the complex textures of woven wool, the finishes of ancient wooden tools, and the subtle chromatic variations of vegetable dyes. Each object was captured from multiple lighting angles, generating comprehensive datasets integrating geometric information and optical properties.

Post-capture processing used artificial intelligence algorithms specialized in 3D reconstruction. The photometric data was analyzed by convolutional neural networks capable of deducing material properties (BRDF) from multiple lighting photographs. This approach made it possible to generate 3D models that were not only geometrically accurate, but also physically plausible in their interaction with light.

The use of machine learning techniques significantly optimized the process of cleaning and optimizing the models. Geometric completion algorithms were used to reconstruct missing or damaged parts of the artifacts, while super-resolution systems enriched the textural definition of the final models. This processing phase perfectly illustrates the efficient use of AI: the automation of repetitive tasks freed up students for work with higher creative added value.

The generated 3D models were integrated into an innovative museum experience combining augmented reality and interactive interfaces. The designed tour allows visitors to view objects from all angles using interactive 3D visualizations and access enriched contextual information through an app and then a virtual online museum tour. This approach goes beyond a simple exhibition to create an immersive educational experience. Visitors can understand the technical complexity of traditional weaving by virtually manipulating the tools, observing the characteristic wear and tear of carding combs, or analyzing the microscopic structure of wool fibers.

For the students, this project represented a unique opportunity to develop a deep understanding of the creative potential of AI. The process enabled them to gain a positive understanding of AI technologies and master the ethical issues related to heritage digitization. The students particularly appreciated the ethical dimension of this project: unlike some questionable uses of generative AI, here the technology was explicitly used to preserve and promote endangered heritage, in a framework of respectful collaboration with the traditional holders of this knowledge. The approach developed represents a break with traditional methods of heritage documentation. By enabling faithful reproduction not only of forms but also of materials and their light behavior, it offers new perspectives for the development of educational programs that raise awareness among future designers of important societal, economic, and social issues. This initiative demonstrates that the efficient and positive use of AI is not only possible but particularly fruitful when it is anchored in meaningful projects that combine technological innovation, heritage preservation, and the development of critical skills in new generations of designers and cultural mediators.

This FAM project embodies a path to profound transformation in educational paradigms, as it reflects the possibilities of AI in educational practice and its ability to transcend its status as a technical object to become a catalyst for a rethinking of teaching practices in the university setting. Immersing students in this experience could enable AI to be integrated as a genuine scientific investigation methodology and a tool for comprehensively understanding artisanal skills. This approach could also radically transform the role of the teacher-researcher and offer future designers the opportunity to grasp cultural realities that would otherwise remain inaccessible. In this context, the modeling of heritage data and its processing by specialized algorithms has established a fruitful dialectic between empirical investigation and theoretical conceptualization. In this sense, this experiment could familiarize students with AI tools and present them as mediators for deciphering the semantics of Amazigh motifs and establishing correlations between different cultural expressions, which could guide students as any other cultural mediation tool would. Thus, beyond the stage of educational experimentation, the integration of AI into higher education could profoundly enrich scientific investigation approaches and strengthen the acquisition of cross-disciplinary skills, provided that in-depth training in the use of AI is implemented from the early years of university education.

Conclusion

The era of AI in higher education is no longer a distant prospect but a tangible reality that is establishing itself as an unavoidable social and educational fact. Our research shows that the question is no longer whether to integrate AI into design education, but how to do so in an informed, critical, and creative way. The time for fear and systematic resistance must give way to a proactive and strategic approach to making AI an ally in training the creators of tomorrow.

The results of our qualitative study of Tunisian teachers, combined with the analysis of the FAM project, reveal a historic opportunity for educational transformation. Far from representing a threat to human creativity, AI could become a catalyst for innovation when integrated into thoughtful educational frameworks. The FAM project is a good example of how the most advanced digital technologies could be used to preserve and promote endangered cultural heritage, thus creating links between tradition and innovation. However, the need to develop teachers' skills towards a role as critical mediators and designers of innovative learning situations now appears to be the cornerstone of this transformation. The teacher of the future will not be replaced by AI, but will see their role enhanced to include higher value-added functions: architect of personalized learning paths, facilitator of hybrid creative processes, and guardian of ethics and critical thinking.

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